

Studies on Synthesis and Toxicity to Fish of some Chalcones, Flavonols and Flavones

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CHALCONES^{1,2}, α,β -unsaturated ketones³, flavones⁴ and flavonoids⁴ have been reported to possess various biological activities. Hydroxychalcones⁵, hydroxyflavones⁶ and flavanones have been found to possess antifungal and antibacterial activities. Considering these facts, we have synthesised some chalcones, flavones and flavonols and tested for their toxicity to fish.

Condensation of 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl- and 5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methylacetophenones with 1-naphthaldehyde and 2-methoxy-1-naphthaldehyde in alkali yielded the corresponding chalcones (1a-d) (Scheme 1). Similarly, chalcone 1e was also prepared from 2'-hydroxy-3',5'-diiodoacetophenone

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) EtOH/KOH, HCl, (ii) H₂O₂/MeOH/NaOH, (iii) SeO₂/isoamyl alcohol.

and 4-bromo-2-methoxybenzaldehyde. The purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc. These compounds gave pink colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid, positive Wilson test⁷ and violet-red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. Ir spectra of these compounds showed bands at 1 550-1 600 (C=C conjugated) and 1 630-1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O). These assignments are in agreements with those observed reported⁸ in case of chalcones. Further, chalcones (1a-d) on selenium dioxide oxidation afforded the corresponding flavones (2a-d). These compounds did not give violet colouration with ferric chloride solution and pink colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. Their ir spectra showed a band near 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

All the above chalcones were successfully converted to the corresponding flavonols (3a-d) by hydrogen peroxide oxidation in methanolic sodium hydroxide solution (Algar-Flynn-Oyamada reaction). This compounds gave characteristic greenish yellow fluorescence in ethanolic solution as well as with concentrated sulphuric acid and brown colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride. Their ir spectra showed bands at 1 620-1 650 (C=O) and 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH). Further, structures of compounds have been supported by the pmr spectra of chalcone (1b), flavone (2b) and flavonol (3b) as the representative cases.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian FT-80 spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard.

1-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-3-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (1b): To an equimolar (0.01 mol) mixture of 2'-hydroxy-5'-methylacetophenone and 2-methoxy-1-naphthaldehyde dissolved in ethanol (30-40 ml) was added a 10% KOH solution (10-15 ml) and the reaction mixture was kept at 60° for 16 h. It was then diluted with ice-cold water and acidified with concentrated HCl. The resulting yellow solid was washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (80%), m.p. 133°; ν_{max} 1 645-1 650 (C=O) and 1 565-1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 10.1 (1H, s, OH) and 6.4-8.2 (9H, m, ArH). Similarly other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

6-Methyl-2-(2'-methoxy-1'-naphthyl)flavone (2b): A mixture of the chalcone 1b (1 g), selenium dioxide (1.5 g) and isoamyl alcohol (15 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath at 135-45° for 16 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered hot. On cooling, the resulting yellowish solid was crystallisation from dioxane, (75%), m.p. 181°; ν_{max} 1 640 (C=O) and 1 320-1 380 cm⁻¹ (γ -pyron ring); δ (CDCl₃) 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.53 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.8-8.23 (9H, m, ArH). Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	114	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂
1b	133	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂
1c	170	85	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl
1d	189	90	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl
1e	218	88	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ BrI
2a	154	78	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂
2b	181	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂
2c	182	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl
2d	202	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl
3a	201	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂
3b	255	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂
3c	233	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl
3d	295	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl
3e	249	70	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₄ BrI ₂

6-Methyl-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-methoxy-1'-naphthyl)-flavonol (3b): The chalcone (1b; 0.01 mol) in methanol (15–20 ml) was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (5–10 ml; 5%) and the reaction mixture cooled in ice-bath. Hydrogen peroxide (10–15 ml; 20 vol) was then added and the reaction mixture kept in ice-salt freezing mixture for 3–4 h and overnight at room temperature. The colour of the reaction mixture changed from dark red to deep yellow. It was filtered to isolate other products (mostly aurones) and then the filtrate was diluted with ice-cold water and acidified with HCl (1 : 1). The resulting light yellowish solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from dioxane, (70%) m.p. 255°; ν_{\max} 1 620–1 630 (C=O) and 3 300–3 320 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.9 (1H, s, OH) and 6.7–7.8 (9H, m, ArH). Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

Toxicity study: For the evaluation of biological activity of compounds, the use of fish as a test animal have been reported by some workers¹⁰.

The basic static acute toxicity test method¹¹ was employed for testing the compounds for their toxicity to a fresh water fish *Barbus ticto*. The fish samples were collected from Godavari river near Nanded (Maharashtra) which were about 1.0–1.5 inch in length and 2–3 g in weight. Five fishes were employed for each experiment.

Dioxane solution of the compound (30 mg of each compound dissolved in 1 ml dioxane) was mixed with water (1 dm³). Then 5 fishes were introduced into it and the time-period required for their death was recorded. The control experiment conducted by using dioxane showed that a concentration of 1% is harmless to the fish over a period of 24 h. From the observation it is found that halogenoflavonols are more toxic than their corresponding chalcones.

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